

Python code to generate Resemblance-Ranking Library

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from collections import Counter
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import re
from scipy import sparse
import gc
#####
### Load and Transform Data ###
#####
# filepath to the fasta file
FASTA_FILEPATH = r'uniprot-proteome%3AUP000005640+reviewed%3Ayes.fasta'
def load_proteom(filepath = FASTA_FILEPATH):
    """Loads the content of the fasta file, parses its content, and returns a list of protein strings."""
    # read content of the fasta file
    with open(filepath, 'r') as f:
        content = f.read()
    # retrieve the list of proteins from the file content:
    # - split file content on the annotation lines (they start with the '>' symbol and end with a new line symbol '\n')
    # - empty lines are skipped (actually the first one, since the content starts with an annotation line)
    # - new line symbols '\n' within each protein chain are replaced by an empty string ""
    protein_list = [protein.replace('\n', "") for protein in re.split(r'>.*?\n', content) if protein]
    print(f'Loaded {len(protein_list)} protein sequences')
    return protein_list
def preprocess_proteom(protein_list):
    """Preprocesses protein sequences: - replaces Selenocysteine (U) by Cystein (C)."""
    ### replace Selenocysteine (U) by Cystein (C)
    # get a count of Us in the proteom to be replaced for notification purpose
    u_count = sum(protein.count('U') for protein in protein_list)
    # perform replace
    protein_list = [protein.replace('U', 'C') for protein in protein_list]
    print(f'Replaced {u_count} Selenocysteines (U) by Cysteines (C)')
    return protein_list
# load and preprocess proteom
protein_list = load_proteom()
protein_list = preprocess_proteom(protein_list)
#####
### Retrieve Peptide Candidates ###
#####
# number of peptides to be selected from the proteom into the final library
NUM_PEPTIDES = 100_000
# length of peptides in the final library
K = 10
def get_k_mer_candidates(protein_list, k = K):
    """Returns a list of unique overlapping k-mer fragments in the proteom."""
    # instantiate a list of k-meric peptides
    peptide_candidates = []
    # iterate over protein sequences
    for protein in protein_list:
        # extend peptide list by overlapping peptides from the protein
        peptide_candidates.extend([protein[i : i + k] for i in range(len(protein) - k + 1)])
    # get a list of all unique overlapping k-meric peptides from the proteom
    peptide_candidates = list(set(peptide_candidates))
    print(f'Total number of candidates: {len(peptide_candidates):,}')
    return peptide_candidates
# get a list of all unique overlapping K-meric peptides from the proteom
peptide_candidates = get_k_mer_candidates(protein_list = protein_list)
#####
### Prepare Supplementary Data ###
#####
def get_look_up_lists(protein_list, k = K):
    """Gets a Counter of unique proteom fragments
    with the length of m (1 <= m <= k). In other words,
    counts the total number of unique fragment occurrences in the whole proteom. Retrieves the lists of unique m-meric fragments and their respective counts:
    a) the list of unique m-meric fragments will be used as a look-up tokenizer, where the position index of each fragment will be a unique token value of the respective m-
    mer fragment. This list will be used to encode peptide candidates.
    b) the list of the respective counts will be used to get fragments weights for calculation of peptide-proteom similarities. """
    print('Please wait... This may take ca. 60 seconds and up to 12 GB RAM at the peak')
    # instantiate a Counter object
    m_mer_counter = Counter()
    # iterate over the range of m-mer lengths
    for m in range(1, k + 1):
        print(m, end = ', ' if m < k else '\n')
        # generate a list of m-meric peptides
        peptide_list = [protein[i : i + m] for protein in protein_list for i in range(len(protein) - m + 1)]
        # update the counter
        m_mer_counter.update(peptide_list)
    # get the lists (not tuples) of unique fragments and their respective counts
    fragment_list, count_list = map(list, zip(*m_mer_counter.items()))
    print('Total number of unique fragments: {len(fragment_list):,}')
    return fragment_list, count_list
# get a list of unique m_meric fragments and a list of their respective counts in the proteom
fragment_list, count_list = get_look_up_lists(protein_list)
# gain some memory
del protein_list
gc.collect()
def get_fragment_weights(fragment_list, count_list, k = K):
    """Transforms counts list to the list of fragments weights. Weighting takes into account combinatorial probability of an m_mer fragment, total number of fragments of
    such length in the proteom, as well as proteomic 'entropy' of the respective m-level."""
    # get a list of lengths of the respective m_fragments in the fragment list
    # these values will be used as keys to access m-level-specific parameters calculated below
    fragment_length_list = [len(fragment) for fragment in fragment_list]
    #####
    ### GET M_DESCRIPTOR ###
    #####
    """Retrieves the total number of m-meric fragments that can be derived from the whole proteom with m length ranging from 1 to k inclusively, as well as the number
    of unique m-meric fragments present in the proteom. Results are two dictionaries in form {'m' : total_number_of_fragments} and {'m' :
    number_of_unique_fragments}."""
    # instantiate an empty dictionary of total counts and unique counts
    num_total_dict = {}
    num_unique_dict = {}
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# iterate over the range of m-lengths
for m in range(1, k + 1):
    # get indices of those fragments which have length of m
    m_len_indices = [idx for idx, token_length in enumerate(fragment_length_list) if token_length == m]
    # get total number of all m-meric fragments
    num_total = sum([count_list[idx] for idx in m_len_indices])
    # get number of unique m-meric fragments
    num_unique = len(m_len_indices)
    # update respective dictionaries
    num_total_dict[m] = num_total
    num_unique_dict[m] = num_unique
    print(f'M-mer length {m}: num_total {num_total}, num_unique {num_unique}')
#####
### GET LEVEL WEIGHTS ###
#####
"""Returns a dictionary of level weights in form {'m' : level_weight}. For details, check another notebook script."""
# get a Series of unique counts only
num_unique_series = pd.Series(num_unique_dict)
# add the number of m-mers of 0 length
num_unique_series[0] = 0
# sort series values by index
num_unique_series.sort_index(inplace = True)
# get a series of the first derivative of unique_counts
num_unique_prime_series = num_unique_series - num_unique_series.shift(1)
# normalize the values so that the sum equals to one
num_unique_prime_series = num_unique_prime_series / num_unique_prime_series.sum()
# convert series to dictionary for all the ites except of 0th one
level_weights_dict = num_unique_prime_series[1:].to_dict()
print('\nCombinatorial entropy factor:')
for key, value in level_weights_dict.items():
    print(f'M-mer length {key}: level weight {value}')
#####
### GET M-FRAGMENT WEIGHT LIST ###
#####
# construct a list of weights for the respective m_mer fragments;
# the weight of each fragment:
# - is proportional to the number of its occurances in the whole proteom
# - is proportional to the number of unique fragments having the same length as the weighted fragment
# (this compensates smaller counts of longer fragments)
# - is proportional to the additional combinatorial entropy this m-level gains in contrast to the
# previous one (gives higher weight to fragments with a length of 6 and 5)
# - is reverse proportional to the total number of m-meric fragments in the proteom
weight_list = [count_list[idx] * level_weights_dict[m] * num_unique_dict[m] / num_total_dict[m]
               for idx, m in enumerate(fragment_length_list)]
return weight_list
weight_list = get_fragment_weights(fragment_list, count_list)
# gain some memory
del count_list
gc.collect()
#####
### Encode Peptide Candidates and Fragment Weights ###
#####
# define minimum and maximum lengths of fragments used in encoding peptides
# (required mainly to overcome memory limitations)
# as we would see from fragment weights, those with the length of 1 and 2 are the least weighted but they
# account for the most frequent occurrence in encodings
K_MIN = 1 # 3
# 10-meric peptide fragments are rather unique (>95% of them are single counts). Hence for >95% of encoded peptides,
# considering m=10 would correspond to just adding a constant weight for nearly each peptide
K_MAX = 10 # 9
def encode_candidates(peptide_candidates, fragment_list, k = K, k_min = K_MIN, k_max = K_MAX):
    """Encodes each peptide candidate as a list of included unique fragment indices from the fragment_list. For instance, a peptide ABCD, which can be represented as
    a set of the following fragments: {A, B, C, D, AB, BC, CD, ABC, BCD, ABCD}, will be encoded as a list of tokens which represent the indices of the respective
    fragments in the fragment_list."""
    print('Encoding may take ca. 8 mins.')
    # to speed up encoding, create an {'m_fragment': idx} dictionary
    index_look_up_dict = {m_fragment : idx for idx, m_fragment in enumerate(fragment_list)}
    # instantiate a list of encoded peptide candidates
    encoded_candidates = []
    print('Processed candidates: ', end = '')
    # iterate over peptide candidates
    for idx, peptide in enumerate(peptide_candidates):
        # represent each peptide as a list of unique m_meric fragments with 1 <= m <= k
        m_fragment_set = set([peptide[i : i + m] for m in range(k_min, k_max + 1) for i in range(k - m + 1)])
        # get encoded representation of the respective peptide as a list (sets simply don't fit into memory)
        encoded_peptide = [index_look_up_dict[m_fragment] for m_fragment in m_fragment_set]
        # append encoded peptide to the list of encoded_candidates
        encoded_candidates.append(encoded_peptide)
        if idx % 1_000_000 == 0:
            print(f'{idx:}', end = ', ')
    print('\nDone')
    return encoded_candidates
# encode peptide candidates
encoded_candidates = encode_candidates(peptide_candidates, fragment_list)
# gain some memory
del fragment_list
gc.collect()
def get_sparse_matrix(encoded_candidates):
    """Generates and returns a sparse
    one-hot-encoder matrix with the shape
    of (number_of_peptide_candidates x number_of_encoding_fragments).
    Each row represents an encoded peptide candidate,
    each column represents a unique m-fragment of the proteom."""
    # instantiate row and col lists
    row = []
    col = []
    # iterate over encoded candidates
    for idx, encoded_peptide in enumerate(encoded_candidates):
        # append encoding indices
        col.extend(encoded_peptide)
        row.extend([idx]*len(encoded_peptide))
    # transform row and col to numpy array, get data array
    row = np.array(row, dtype = np.uint32)

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col = np.array(col, dtype = np.uint32)
data = np.ones(row.size, dtype = np.uint8)
# generate a sparse CSR matrix
encoded_candidates_matrix = sparse.csr_matrix((data, (row, col)), dtype=np.uint8)
print(f'Encoded peptide candidates by a sparse matrix of shape: {encoded_candidates_matrix.get_shape()}')
return encoded_candidates_matrix
# represent encoded candidates as a sparse matrix
encoded_candidates_matrix = get_sparse_matrix(encoded_candidates)
# gain some memory
del encoded_candidates
gc.collect()
# represent fragment weights as a numpy array
weight_array = np.array(weight_list)
print(f'Encoded fragment weights as a numpy array of shape: {weight_array.shape}')
# gain some memory
del weight_list
gc.collect()
#####
### Library Build-Up ###
#####
def build_up_library(encoded_candidates_matrix, weight_array, peptide_candidates, num_peptides = NUM_PEPTIDES):
    """Iteratively assembles peptide library from those peptide candidates which incrementally increase the similarity score to the whole proteome. Returns a list of
    tuples (index_of_added_peptide, similarity_gain). """
    # get a copy of the encoded_candidates_matrix and the weight_array
    # (for the sake of not violating what has been done till this point)
    # The latter array will be continuously altered during library build-up
    encoded_candidates_matrix_copy = encoded_candidates_matrix.copy()
    weight_array_copy = weight_array.copy()
    # instantiate a peptide library list
    library = []
    # iterate over the number of peptides to be added to the library
    for idx in range(num_peptides):
        # Selection process is done in two steps:
        #####
        ### 1. best candidate selection ###
        #####
        # get a vector of potentially gained similarities for all the peptide candidates
        # if they would be added to the library
        similarity_gain = encoded_candidates_matrix_copy.dot(weight_array_copy)
        # get the index and value of the candidate with the highest gain
        # e.g. the one which contributes most to the similarity score
        best_candidate_idx = np.argmax(similarity_gain)
        extra_gain = similarity_gain[best_candidate_idx]
        # the latter will be used for informative purpose, since it can reveal an optimum size of the library (NUM_PEPTIDES)
        # 'save' reference to the selected peptide
        # library.append((best_candidate_idx, extra_gain))
        #####
        ### 2. elimination of repetitions ###
        #####
        # get indices of those columns which represent fragments to be excluded from consideration
        # in other words, columns which encoded the recently selected candidate
        eliminate_cols = encoded_candidates_matrix_copy[best_candidate_idx].nonzero()[1]
        # for the first 100 iterations only: reduce significantly the size of the sparse matrix (mainly due to removing highly frequent 1-/2-meric fragments)
        if idx < 100:
            # get indices of those 'data' elements which are located in any of the eliminate columns
            zero_mask = np.isin(encoded_candidates_matrix_copy.nonzero()[1], eliminate_cols)
            # zero those elements
            encoded_candidates_matrix_copy.data[zero_mask] = 0
            # drop those elements
            encoded_candidates_matrix_copy.eliminate_zeros()
        # for all the iterations, zero up fragment weights (kind of 'switch off' those fragments from calculation of the similarity gains)
        weight_array_copy[eliminate_cols] = 0
        #####
        ### dump interim results ###
        #####
        # dump recently added peptide to a txt file
        with open('library.txt', 'a', encoding='utf-8') as f:
            f.write(f'{best_candidate_idx}\t{peptide_candidates[best_candidate_idx]}\t{extra_gain}\n')
        # force garbage collection every 1000 cycles
        if idx % 1_000 == 0:
            gc.collect()
    print('\nDone')
    return library
build_up_library(encoded_candidates_matrix, weight_array, peptide_candidates)
print("Script execution completed!")

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